

ВООРУЖЕНИЕ ВОЙСКА АМИРА ТЕМУРА И СПОСОБЫ ЕГО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ

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Аннотация: Полководческое мастерство Амира Темура и его славный жизненный путь были высоко оценены не только нашей страной, но и руководителями других стран как образец. Он был не только основателем великой империи, но и одним из профессиональных личностей, создавших свою собственную самобытную стратегию ведения боя.

Ключевые слова: войско, артиллерия, копье, шлем, доспехи, меч, лук, стрела, десять, сто, тысяча.

WEAPONS OF AMIR TEMUR'S ARMY AND METHODS OF THEIR USE

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Annotation: Amir Temur's skill as a military commander and his glorious way of life have been highly recognized not only by our country but also by the leaders of other countries as a perfect example. He was not only the founder of the great empire, but also was one of the professional individuals who created his own distinctive strategy of battle.

Keywords: army, artillery, spear, helmet, armor, sword, bow, arrow, ten, hundred, thousand.

Although the army formed by Amir Temur was close to the system of Genghis Khan's army in terms of its organizational system, it was distinguished by the following features: Amir Temur's army was a people's army, it was not as general as it was during Genghis Khan's reign. During Genghis Khan's reign, the army was based on nomads. During the reign of Amir Temur, nomads supplied cavalry and archers. But at the same time, the sedentary population makes up the bulk of the population. Thus, due to the frequency and scale of the wars, peasants, artisans and other categories of the settled population were called up for military service along with the herdsmen. The infantry played a role in the coup. During the reign of Genghis Khan, there were no fullfledged infantry. Amir Temur was one of the first in the East to introduce artillery (rad) into the army. The introduction of a new type of firearm allowed to create artillery units.) number reached several thousand. Artillery is used to crush enemy forces and equipment, as well as to besiege castles and citadels. They were set up in the most important sections of the siege line. Special infantry troops were skillfully deployed in the mountains. The army was divided into nine and seven divisions. The army consisted of women, who stood in line with the men during the battle, and gained fame and courage. The cavalry units often differed from each other not only in the colors of their clothes, flags and emblems, but also in the color of their horses. This difference played a major role in the management of the army during the war. The superiority of the enemy over the enemy was ensured by the high mobility of the cavalry and their skillful maneuvering by Amir Temur. , a long siege of the besieged cities, the conquest of individual villages, 251 districts, towns and provinces, the pursuit of the enemy until it is completely crushed, the appointment of his loyalists to rule the occupied territories. Successive implementation of strategic goals brought Amir Temur many victories. His great contribution to the development of military work was the introduction of completely new cavalry units (kunbul, kumbul), which not only defended their wings. but also to bypass the enemy wings and strike the front. formed an armored unit of the army and was divided into light and heavy cavalry. Light cavalry armed with bows, arrows, and swords engaged in reconnaissance, guarding, and, if necessary, advancing the enemy. Heavy cavalry of elite warriors and nobles fought against the main armies of the enemy. The riders were armed with spears, helmets, armor, swords, bows, and arrows. Before the military march, Amir Temur usually convened a military council, which was attended by military leaders, beys, and emirs. He was recruited from different parts of the country by a special order (muchalka) issued by the Supreme Commander-in-Chief's adjutant (tavachi). In addition to recruiting fighters, the task force was to monitor the deployment of troops, their movement, and the order of battle. Amir Temur had his army and everything he needed to fight paid special attention to the provision of accommodation in the camps governors of provinces, districts and cities, The chiefs of the fortresses (darugha) arrived at the predetermined place (the land of Miod) with their armies, equipment, and food within the time specified in the list. Before the military campaign in Kipchak

(1390–1391), Amir Temur ordered his deputies to provide the army with food, weapons, and other necessities for a long time. Each warrior had one bow, thirty arrows, one commander, one shield, and one reserve horse. During the voyage, each soldier was given one tent, two shovels, a sickle, a saw, an ax, and a hundred needles. Each soldier also carried a rope, leather, and a cauldron. Ordinary soldiers carried one tent for eighteen people during the journey. Each of them had two horses with him, carrying a bow, armor, sword, arrow, sack, ten needles, an ax, a saw, and a leather bag.

The warriors were in tents of five. Each of the supplies included a helmet, armor, sword, bow, arrow, and horse. The ten beys are in a separate tent. He is armed with armor, sword, bow, bow. He was allowed to take five extra horses with him. A hundred tents were also given to him. His weapons consisted of swords, bows, armor, arrows, hammers, clubs, and clubs (woven shirts made of wire rings). One hundred beys were given ten additional horses. A thousand beys had an umbrella in addition to a tent, and their weapons consisted of spears, swords, arrows, helmets, armor (chax), and poles. During the military campaigns, the infantry moved armed with swords, bows and the required number of bow arrows. Butchers, cooks, vendors, bakers, barley and fruit sellers moved with the army. The soldiers were served by mobile baths. The march was attended not only by fighters, but also by a large number of military administrations. There were blacksmiths, gunsmiths, carpenters, tanners, diggers, farm laborers, and others. 252 Amir Temur's army was followed by a large unarmed crowd. After the decision was made to mobilize the army, the fighters arrived at the designated place with their families, equipment and food. newcomers. In the center of the camp, Supreme Commander Sharofuddin Ali Yazdi reported that in the prescribed order of the trip (murchil) each onbegi, yuzbegi, mingbegi and district begi (commander of the army of 10 thousand) were assigned to their positions. He acted with strict adherence to discipline. Violators were severely punished and even sentenced to death. When they stopped to rest, they were usually surrounded by chariots with chains and ropes. Trenches have been dug and barricades have been erected. With the appearance of the enemy, the warriors left their positions and moved in a fighting order against the enemy, wing (dark), left wing (bell), center (hand), arergard (whistle). They were followed by carts loaded with necessities. In one of the main places there is a place for crossing the water. The crossing is guarded by security guards. The army crossed the river in units. During the crossing, the fighters used boats, mesh or pontoon bridges. During the distribution of booty in Amir Temur's army, anyone who acted arbitrarily was severely punished, even if he was a close person of Sahibkiran. All his property was confiscated and he was executed. Only after permission was given did each participant in the march, regardless of its category and level, be entitled to an equally distributed portion of the booty. Amir Temur's last two of the three marches against the Stop (1389, 1391, 1395), especially in 1395, Terek The destruction of the river is of great importance in terms of the development of

martial arts. In the winter of 1391, Sahibkiran decided to avert the threat posed by Tokhtamish and prevent the Golden Horde from forming an alliance with the Egyptian states against Timur's state. He ordered an army to be mobilized to begin the march against the Stop. Food stocks have been stockpiled for the army. The assembled army left Samarkand and crossed the Syrdarya on a bridge near the city of Khojand. In Tashkent, Temur inspected the army. The fighters were ordered to have the necessary weapons and equipment. On January 19, 1391, during a military parade, Amir Temur declared war on the Jochi nation. He lined up his army and assigned commanders to each column.

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